

Colored Membership Graphs and Canonical Forms for Symmetry-Reduced Power-Set Hierarchies

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Abstract

We introduce a quotient of hereditarily finite set hierarchies that simultaneously removes blockwise relabeling and pure unary nesting $x, \{x\}, \{\{x\}\}, \dots$, and prove that rooted colored membership graphs provide complete canonical normal forms for its equivalence classes.

Keywords. Hereditarily finite sets; unary-nesting reduction; symmetry reduction; colored membership graphs; canonical forms; orbit enumeration.

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1 Introduction

Figure 1: Two subsets in the first layer with the same block profile, highlighted by connected selection lines.

Let

$$A_N = \{a_1, \dots, a_N\} \quad (1)$$

be a finite set of atoms, and define the iterated power-set hierarchy

$$S_0 = A_N, \quad S_{n+1} = \mathcal{P}(S_n), \quad \mathcal{H}_N = \bigcup_{n \geq 0} S_n. \quad (2)$$

Thus \mathcal{H}_N is the class of hereditarily finite sets generated from A_N .

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Figure 2: unary-nesting reduction removes pure unary nesting but preserves genuine branching.

Fix a partition

$$A_N = B_1 \sqcup \cdots \sqcup B_r, \quad |B_i| = n_i, \quad n_1 + \cdots + n_r = N, \quad (3)$$

and let

$$G_\pi := \text{Sym}(B_1) \times \cdots \times \text{Sym}(B_r) \quad (4)$$

be the corresponding block-preserving symmetry group. The goal of this note is to quotient \mathcal{H}_N simultaneously by relabeling inside the blocks and by pure unary nesting

$$x, \{x\}, \{\{x\}\}, \dots \quad (5)$$

Hereditarily finite sets and their recursive structure are classical; see, for example, [1, 2]. Canonical labeling for finite graphs is also classical; see [3, 4, 5]. The point here is that the quotient obtained from blockwise symmetry and unary-nesting reduction admits complete rooted graph normal forms.

2 The reduced hierarchy

The action of G_π on \mathcal{H}_N is defined recursively by

$$\sigma \cdot a = \sigma(a) \quad (a \in A_N), \quad (6)$$

and

$$\sigma \cdot x = \{\sigma \cdot y : y \in x\} \quad (x \notin A_N). \quad (7)$$

We use the usual rank on \mathcal{H}_N :

$$\text{rank}(a) = 0 \quad (a \in A_N), \quad (8)$$

and for $x \notin A_N$,

$$\text{rank}(x) = \sup\{\text{rank}(y) + 1 : y \in x\}. \quad (9)$$

Definition 2.1 (Unary core). Define $\text{core} : \mathcal{H}_N \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_N$ recursively on rank. For $a \in A_N$, set

$$\text{core}(a) = a. \quad (10)$$

For $x \notin A_N$, let

$$E_x := \{\text{core}(y) : y \in x\}. \quad (11)$$

Then define

$$\text{core}(x) = \begin{cases} u, & \text{if } E_x = \{u\}, \\ E_x, & \text{if } |E_x| \neq 1. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Theorem 2.2 (Idempotence and equivariance). For every $x \in \mathcal{H}_N$ and every $\sigma \in G_\pi$,

$$\text{core}(\text{core}(x)) = \text{core}(x) \quad (13)$$

and

$$\text{core}(\sigma \cdot x) = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(x). \quad (14)$$

Figure 3: Let $A_6 = B_1 \sqcup B_2 \sqcup B_3$ be a partition into three symmetry blocks, and consider the element $x = \{u_1, u_2, u_3\} \in S_3$, where $u_1 = \{\{a_1\}\}$, $u_2 = \{\{a_3, a_5\}\}$, and $u_3 = \{\{a_2, a_4\}, \{a_6\}\}$. Its unary core is $\text{core}(x) = \{a_1, \{a_3, a_5\}, \{\{a_2, a_4\}, a_6\}\}$, and the associated colored membership graph is a rooted tree. For example the rooted colored membership graphs associated with $c = \text{core}(x)$ and $d = \text{core}(y)$ are color-preserving isomorphic. This isomorphism is realized by a relabeling inside each symmetry block, namely by the permutation $\sigma = (a_1 a_2)(a_3 a_4)(a_5 a_6) \in G_\pi$, which sends c to d and matches every vertex u of $M_\pi(c)$ with the vertex $\sigma \cdot u$ of $M_\pi(d)$.

Proof. We argue by induction on $\text{rank}(x)$.

If $x = a \in A_N$, both identities are immediate.

Assume $x \notin A_N$, and write

$$E_x = \{\text{core}(y) : y \in x\}. \quad (15)$$

For idempotence, if $E_x = \{u\}$, then $\text{core}(x) = u$, and the induction hypothesis gives

$$\text{core}(\text{core}(x)) = \text{core}(u) = u = \text{core}(x). \quad (16)$$

If $|E_x| \neq 1$, then $\text{core}(x) = E_x$. Every $v \in E_x$ has the form $v = \text{core}(y)$ for some $y \in x$, so $\text{core}(v) = v$ by induction. Hence

$$\{\text{core}(v) : v \in E_x\} = E_x, \quad (17)$$

and since $|E_x| \neq 1$,

$$\text{core}(\text{core}(x)) = \text{core}(E_x) = E_x = \text{core}(x). \quad (18)$$

For equivariance,

$$E_{\sigma \cdot x} = \{\text{core}(\sigma \cdot y) : y \in x\} = \{\sigma \cdot \text{core}(y) : y \in x\} = \sigma \cdot E_x, \quad (19)$$

where the middle equality follows from the induction hypothesis. If $E_x = \{u\}$, then $E_{\sigma \cdot x} = \{\sigma \cdot u\}$, so

$$\text{core}(\sigma \cdot x) = \sigma \cdot u = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(x). \quad (20)$$

If $|E_x| \neq 1$, then $|E_{\sigma \cdot x}| \neq 1$, and thus

$$\text{core}(\sigma \cdot x) = E_{\sigma \cdot x} = \sigma \cdot E_x = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(x). \quad (21)$$

□

Definition 2.3 (Reduced equivalence). For $x, y \in \mathcal{H}_N$, define

$$x \equiv_\pi y \iff \exists \sigma \in G_\pi \text{ such that } \text{core}(y) = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(x). \quad (22)$$

Proposition 2.4. The relation \equiv_π is an equivalence relation on \mathcal{H}_N .

Proof. Reflexivity is immediate. Symmetry follows from group inversion and Theorem 2.2. Transitivity follows from group multiplication and Theorem 2.2. □

Definition 2.5. For $n \geq 0$, define

$$C_n := \{\text{core}(x) : x \in S_n\}, \quad R_n := \{[x]_{\equiv_\pi} : x \in S_n\}. \quad (23)$$

Theorem 2.6 (Core representatives). *For every $n \geq 0$, the map*

$$C_n/G_\pi \longrightarrow R_n, \quad G_\pi \cdot c \longmapsto [c]_{\equiv_\pi}, \quad (24)$$

is a well-defined bijection. In particular, every class in R_n has a core-reduced representative, unique up to the action of G_π .

Proof. If $c \in C_n$, then $c = \text{core}(x)$ for some $x \in S_n$, hence c represents a class in R_n . If $d = \sigma \cdot c$ with $\sigma \in G_\pi$, then Theorem 2.2 gives

$$\text{core}(d) = \text{core}(\sigma \cdot c) = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(c) = \sigma \cdot c = d, \quad (25)$$

so $c \equiv_\pi d$. Thus the map is well defined on orbits.

Surjectivity is immediate from $x \equiv_\pi \text{core}(x)$.

For injectivity, suppose $c, d \in C_n$ determine the same reduced class. Then for some $\sigma \in G_\pi$,

$$\text{core}(d) = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(c). \quad (26)$$

Since c and d are fixed by core, it follows that

$$d = \sigma \cdot c. \quad (27)$$

□

Theorem 2.7 (Recursive description of the reduced layers). *For every $n \geq 0$,*

$$C_{n+1} = C_n \cup \{E \subseteq C_n : |E| \neq 1\}. \quad (28)$$

In particular,

$$C_n \subseteq C_{n+1} \quad (n \geq 0). \quad (29)$$

Proof. Let $z \in C_{n+1}$. Then $z = \text{core}(x)$ for some $x \in S_{n+1} = \mathcal{P}(S_n)$. If

$$E_x := \{\text{core}(y) : y \in x\} \subseteq C_n, \quad (30)$$

then either $E_x = \{u\}$, in which case $z = u \in C_n$, or $|E_x| \neq 1$, in which case $z = E_x \subseteq C_n$ and $|z| \neq 1$. Thus

$$C_{n+1} \subseteq C_n \cup \{E \subseteq C_n : |E| \neq 1\}. \quad (31)$$

Conversely, if $z \in C_n$, choose $y \in S_n$ with $\text{core}(y) = z$. Then $\{y\} \in S_{n+1}$ and

$$\text{core}(\{y\}) = z. \quad (32)$$

If $z = E \subseteq C_n$ with $|E| \neq 1$, choose $y_u \in S_n$ for each $u \in E$ such that $\text{core}(y_u) = u$, and set

$$x := \{y_u : u \in E\} \in S_{n+1}. \quad (33)$$

Then

$$\{\text{core}(y) : y \in x\} = E, \quad (34)$$

so $\text{core}(x) = E = z$. □

Corollary 2.8. *Each C_n is finite.*

Proof. By induction on n , using Theorem 2.7. □

3 Rooted colored membership digraphs

Definition 3.1. *Let $c \in \mathcal{H}_N$ satisfy $\text{core}(c) = c$. The rooted colored membership digraph of c is*

$$M_\pi(c) = (V_c, E_c, \kappa_c, \rho_c), \quad (35)$$

where

$$V_c := \text{TC}(c) \cup \{c\}, \quad (u, v) \in E_c \iff u \in v, \quad \rho_c := c, \quad (36)$$

and

$$\kappa_c(u) = \begin{cases} i, & \text{if } u \in B_i, \\ 0, & \text{if } u \notin A_N. \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

Definition 3.2. *An isomorphism*

$$\varphi : M_\pi(c) \rightarrow M_\pi(d) \quad (38)$$

is a bijection $\varphi : V_c \rightarrow V_d$ such that for all $u, v \in V_c$,

$$(u, v) \in E_c \iff (\varphi(u), \varphi(v)) \in E_d, \quad (39)$$

$$\kappa_d(\varphi(u)) = \kappa_c(u), \quad (40)$$

and

$$\varphi(\rho_c) = \rho_d. \quad (41)$$

Theorem 3.3 (Reconstruction). *Let*

$$\mathcal{C} := \{c \in \mathcal{H}_N : \text{core}(c) = c\}. \quad (42)$$

For $c, d \in \mathcal{C}$, the following are equivalent:

- (i) $M_\pi(c)$ and $M_\pi(d)$ are isomorphic;
- (ii) there exists $\sigma \in G_\pi$ such that $d = \sigma \cdot c$.

Proof. Assume $M_\pi(c) \cong M_\pi(d)$, and let

$$\varphi : M_\pi(c) \rightarrow M_\pi(d) \quad (43)$$

be an isomorphism.

For each block B_i , the restriction of φ gives a bijection between the color- i atoms occurring in V_c and those occurring in V_d . Extend these partial bijections arbitrarily to permutations

$$\sigma_i \in \text{Sym}(B_i), \quad (44)$$

and set

$$\sigma := (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_r) \in G_\pi. \quad (45)$$

We claim that

$$\varphi(u) = \sigma \cdot u \quad (u \in V_c). \quad (46)$$

The proof is by induction on $\text{rank}(u)$.

If $u \in A_N$, this is true by construction. Assume $u \notin A_N$, and suppose the claim holds for every $w \in u$. Then for $v \in V_d$,

$$v \in \varphi(u) \iff (v, \varphi(u)) \in E_d \iff (\varphi^{-1}(v), u) \in E_c \iff \varphi^{-1}(v) \in u. \quad (47)$$

Hence

$$\varphi(u) = \{\varphi(w) : w \in u\} = \{\sigma \cdot w : w \in u\} = \sigma \cdot u. \quad (48)$$

Since φ preserves roots,

$$d = \rho_d = \varphi(\rho_c) = \varphi(c) = \sigma \cdot c. \quad (49)$$

Conversely, if $d = \sigma \cdot c$ for some $\sigma \in G_\pi$, then

$$u \mapsto \sigma \cdot u \quad (50)$$

is plainly an isomorphism $M_\pi(c) \rightarrow M_\pi(d)$. □

4 Canonical normal forms

Definition 4.1. Fix a canonical labeling procedure Can for finite rooted colored digraphs such that

$$\text{Can}(G) = \text{Can}(H) \iff G \cong H. \quad (51)$$

For $x \in \mathcal{H}_N$, define

$$\text{NF}_\pi(x) := \text{Can}(M_\pi(\text{core}(x))). \quad (52)$$

Theorem 4.2 (Completeness of the normal form). For all $x, y \in \mathcal{H}_N$,

$$x \equiv_\pi y \iff \text{NF}_\pi(x) = \text{NF}_\pi(y). \quad (53)$$

Proof. If $x \equiv_\pi y$, then $\text{core}(y) = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(x)$ for some $\sigma \in G_\pi$. By Theorem 3.3, the rooted colored digraphs

$$M_\pi(\text{core}(x)) \quad \text{and} \quad M_\pi(\text{core}(y)) \quad (54)$$

are isomorphic, hence their canonical labels are equal.

Conversely, if $\text{NF}_\pi(x) = \text{NF}_\pi(y)$, then

$$M_\pi(\text{core}(x)) \cong M_\pi(\text{core}(y)). \quad (55)$$

By Theorem 3.3, there exists $\sigma \in G_\pi$ such that

$$\text{core}(y) = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(x), \quad (56)$$

that is, $x \equiv_\pi y$. □

5 The first layer

Since

$$S_1 = \mathcal{P}(A_N), \quad (57)$$

the first reduced layer admits a simple classification.

Definition 5.1 (Block profile). For $X \subseteq A_N$, define

$$\text{Prof}_\pi(X) := (|X \cap B_1|, \dots, |X \cap B_r|). \quad (58)$$

Theorem 5.2 (Classification of the first layer). For $X, Y \subseteq A_N$,

$$X \equiv_\pi Y \iff \text{Prof}_\pi(X) = \text{Prof}_\pi(Y). \quad (59)$$

Proof. Assume first that

$$\text{Prof}_\pi(X) = \text{Prof}_\pi(Y). \quad (60)$$

For each i , the sets $X \cap B_i$ and $Y \cap B_i$ have the same cardinality, so there exists

$$\sigma_i \in \text{Sym}(B_i) \quad (61)$$

with $\sigma_i(X \cap B_i) = Y \cap B_i$. Thus

$$\sigma := (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_r) \in G_\pi \quad (62)$$

satisfies $\sigma \cdot X = Y$.

If $|X| \neq 1$, then also $|Y| \neq 1$, hence

$$\text{core}(X) = X, \quad \text{core}(Y) = Y, \quad (63)$$

and therefore $X \equiv_\pi Y$. If $|X| = 1$, then $X = \{a\}$, $Y = \{b\}$, and a, b lie in the same block. Hence

$$\text{core}(Y) = b = \sigma \cdot a = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(X), \quad (64)$$

so again $X \equiv_\pi Y$.

Conversely, assume $X \equiv_\pi Y$. Then

$$\text{core}(Y) = \sigma \cdot \text{core}(X) \quad (65)$$

for some $\sigma \in G_\pi$. If neither set is a singleton, then

$$Y = \sigma \cdot X, \quad (66)$$

so the profile is preserved. If $X = \{a\}$ with $a \in B_i$, then $\text{core}(X) = a$, and $\text{core}(Y)$ must be an atom in the same block B_i . Hence Y is also a singleton with its unique element in B_i , so the profiles agree. The case where Y is a singleton is symmetric. \square

Corollary 5.3. The number of reduced classes represented in S_1 is

$$|R_1| = \prod_{i=1}^r (n_i + 1). \quad (67)$$

Proof. The classes are indexed by the admissible profiles

$$(k_1, \dots, k_r), \quad 0 \leq k_i \leq n_i. \quad (68)$$

\square

Corollary 5.4. If $X \subseteq A_N$ has profile

$$\text{Prof}_\pi(X) = (k_1, \dots, k_r), \quad (69)$$

then

$$|\text{Orb}_{G_\pi}(X)| = \prod_{i=1}^r \binom{n_i}{k_i}. \quad (70)$$

Proof. Inside each block B_i , the orbit is determined by the choice of a k_i -element subset. \square

Corollary 5.5. The number of classes represented in S_1 that are not already represented in S_0 is

$$|R_1 \setminus R_0| = \prod_{i=1}^r (n_i + 1) - r. \quad (71)$$

Proof. The layer S_0 contributes exactly the r atom-block classes. \square

6 Conclusion

The quotient framework developed here shows that unary-nesting reduction and blockwise symmetry can be treated in a unified way. At the first level, this leads to a complete classification by block profiles and to explicit counting formulas for the reduced classes. Thus the first reduced layer admits a direct profile classification, whereas the higher layers are naturally governed by a Burnside–Pólya type orbit recursion [6, 7, 8].

From this perspective, the main open task is computational rather than conceptual: to convert the recursive orbit-counting scheme into an effective method for determining $|R_n|$ in higher layers. It would also be natural to investigate whether additional structural invariants can simplify the recursion, detect periodicities, or isolate families of core-reduced objects with especially tractable canonical labels. Finally, the reconstruction theorem suggests algorithmic extensions, including canonical generation procedures and implementations of normal-form computations based on colored membership graphs.

7 Conflict of interest

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

References

- [1] P. Tarau, *A Functional Hitchhiker’s Guide to Hereditarily Finite Sets, Ackermann Encodings, and Pairing Functions*, arXiv:0808.0754, 2008.
- [2] G. Smolka and K. Stark, *Hereditarily Finite Sets in Constructive Type Theory*, *Journal of Automated Reasoning* **58** (2017), 29–62.
- [3] B. D. McKay, *Practical Graph Isomorphism*, *Congressus Numerantium* **30** (1981), 45–87.
- [4] T. Junttila and P. Kaski, *Engineering an Efficient Canonical Labeling Tool for Large and Sparse Graphs*, in *Proceedings of the Ninth Workshop on Algorithm Engineering and Experiments (ALENEX)*, SIAM, 2007, 135–149.
- [5] B. D. McKay and A. Piperno, *Practical Graph Isomorphism, II*, *Journal of Symbolic Computation* **60** (2014), 94–112.
- [6] W. Burnside, *Theory of Groups of Finite Order*, 2nd ed., Cambridge University Press, 1911.
- [7] G. Pólya, *Kombinatorische Anzahlbestimmungen für Gruppen, Graphen und chemische Verbindungen*, *Acta Mathematica* **68** (1937), 145–254.
- [8] F. Harary and E. M. Palmer, *Graphical Enumeration*, Academic Press, New York and London, 1973.